

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Deliverable 3.3

Preliminary report on ALTAI analysis

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Preliminary report on ALTAI analysis

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Partner abbreviations	Full name
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
HI	Háskóli Íslands (University of Iceland)
LOBA	Loba (Portugal)
CHX	Crowd Helix (Ireland)
SVEN	Smart Venice (Italy)
DIGI	Digiotouch (Estonia)

ULEID	Leiden University (The Netherlands)
FARPL	Farplas Automotive (Türkiye)
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Abbreviations**Meaning**

AI	Artificial intelligence
AI Act	Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)
AI HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI
CBR	Case-based reasoning
HR	Human resources
NLP	Natural Language Processing
WP	Work package

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2 Executive Summary

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly shaping recruitment and selection processes, offering the potential to enhance efficiency in hiring. However, growing evidence suggests that AI applications in human resources (HR) often replicate and reinforce diversity biases, leading to social discrimination and violations of fundamental rights. To address these challenges, the BIAS Consortium is developing the Debiaser—an innovative tool to identify and mitigate diversity biases in AI-driven recruitment and selection.

This deliverable presents the first iteration of the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) self-evaluation for different modules of the Debiaser. Section 2 provides an overview of the ALTAI framework and its ethical requirements for AI systems, drawing on findings from Deliverable 2.3. Section 3 presents insights from a preliminary ALTAI assessment conducted with external stakeholders, incorporating user-oriented feedback. Section 4 details the ALTAI self-evaluations performed in a multi-disciplinary collaboration with ULEIDE, BFH, and NTNU for the Debiaser’s natural language processing (NLP) and case-based reasoning (CBR) modules.

Overall, the ALTAI self-evaluation process revealed challenges in assessing NLP-1 and NLP-2, as these tools function as bias detection and mitigation mechanisms rather than decision-making systems. As a result, they do not fully align with ALTAI’s definition of an AI system. In contrast, the CBR module, which serves as a decision-support system for hiring, meets ALTAI’s criteria and was assessed using the official ALTAI platform.

Overall, the evaluation demonstrated strong alignment with ALTAI requirements on privacy and data governance, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, and transparency—reflecting the BIAS Consortium’s extensive efforts in co-creation, AI fairness research, and compliance with legal frameworks. Lower levels of compliance were noted for human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, societal and environmental well-being, and accountability, primarily due to the early stage of the Debiaser’s development, the absence of specific AI components, and the limited applicability of certain ALTAI questions.

Future iterations of the ALTAI evaluation are expected to refine these findings and support further improvements to Debiaser’s design, ensuring its alignment with ethical and regulatory standards for trustworthy AI in recruitment and selection.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has increasingly been integrated into the workforce, particularly in recruitment and selection processes in recent decades. AI applications, which can process vast amounts of information and make decisions at a scale and speed beyond human capacity, are often perceived to enhance efficiency in identifying, attracting, screening, assessing, interviewing, and coordinating with job applicants. However, despite these ambitions, AI-driven hiring processes also present significant challenges (Aloisi, 2023; Fabris et al., 2023; Rigotti & Fosch-Villaronga, 2024; Veldanda et al., 2023).

Within the Work Package (WP) 2 framework, the BIAS Consortium has gathered and analysed growing evidence that these applications tend to replicate and reinforce diversity biases, resulting in social discrimination and other possible violations of fundamental rights (Rigotti et al., 2025). To harness technological advancements in human resources (HR) while ensuring fairness in the workplace, a cautious and proactive approach is essential, with a strong emphasis on identifying and mitigating potential risks. In response, the BIAS Consortium is actively developing an innovative and trustworthy technology called the Debiaser.

This Deliverable reports on the first iteration of the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI), which ULEID has tested with various stakeholders, as well as with the developers and technical partners of the BIAS Consortium responsible for designing the Debiaser. Specifically, Section 2 draws on findings from Deliverable 2.3 to provide a brief refresher on the ALTAI and its foundation. Section 3 presents insights from ALTAI assessments conducted by ULEID with external stakeholders who contributed more user-oriented feedback. Section 4 details the ALTAI evaluations carried out in collaboration with BFH and NTNU for the natural language processing (NLP) and case-based reasoning (CBR) modules of the Debiaser. Finally, the conclusions reflect on these findings and outline future iterations of the ALTAI, which are scheduled for reporting in Month 48.

3 Trustworthy AI and the ALTAI: D2.3 Revisited

As outlined in D2.3 on the final report of the mapping, survey, and expert interviews,¹ the European Commission began promoting the development of trustworthy AI in 2018 to mitigate potential risks posed by AI systems to individuals and society. For this purpose, it convened the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), which contributed to shaping the European AI Strategy (European Commission, 2018). In 2019, the AI HLEG published the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, introducing a framework based on three interrelated dimensions: lawful AI, ethical AI, and robust AI (AI HLEG, 2019). While legal compliance falls within the domain of policymakers and legal experts—currently centred on compliance with Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, commonly known as the AI Act—robustness is regarded as a technical concern. The Guidelines, however, primarily focus on ethical AI (Hohma & Lütge, 2023).

This approach acknowledges that fostering trust in AI governance requires addressing distinct yet interconnected domains, encompassing not only the technology itself but also the broader ecosystem of actors and processes involved in its lifecycle (Díaz-Rodríguez et al., 2023; Radclyffe et al., 2023; Vetter et al., 2023). To operationalise the concept of trustworthy AI, the AI HLEG outlines four ethical principles—human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness, and explicability—alongside seven corresponding requirements (AI HLEG, 2019). These requirements serve as actionable measures, providing a structured approach to ensuring AI systems align with fundamental rights and societal expectations. In brief, the requirements are:

Table 1: Ethical requirements for trustworthy AI

No.	Principle	Concise explanation
1	Human agency and oversight	AI systems should support human autonomy and decision-making.
2	Technical robustness and safety	AI systems should be resilient, reliable, and secure, while being developed to address potential harm.
3	Privacy and data governance	AI systems should ensure adequate protection and processing.
4	Transparency	AI systems should be explainable and traceable to stakeholders.
5	Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	AI systems should avoid unfair bias and being inclusive in their design and use.

¹ All deliverables produced by the BIAS Consortium and approved by the European Commission are available at <<https://www.biasproject.eu/public-reports/>> accessed: 10 March 2025

6	Societal and environmental wellbeing	AI systems should be sustainable, environmentally friendly, based on the interests of society and other sentient beings.
7	Accountability	The design and use of AI systems should be followed by responsibility and legal redress systems.

The ALTAI is structured around these ethical requirements, comprising a comprehensive set of over one hundred questions and corresponding recommendations for AI developers (Gavornik et al., 2022). Designed as a flexible self-evaluation tool, it allows them to tailor its elements to their specific AI systems and operational contexts across various sectors. By implementing the ALTAI, organisations can foster accountability, raise awareness of AI systems’ potential impacts, and prompt adjustments to internal processes to mitigate risks to fundamental rights (Nikolinakos, 2023). Moreover, using the ALTAI encourages AI developers to engage with a diverse range of stakeholders, promoting a more nuanced understanding of the challenges and solutions associated with technological innovation (Gavornik et al., 2022).

In practice, the ALTAI self-evaluation is implemented as a web-based checklist, available at <https://altai.insight-centre.org/>. Each prompt presents a set of options (multiple choice) or allows text-based input, enabling users to verify whether they have investigated and implemented ethical requirements in line with the AI HLEG Guidelines mentioned above. Key concepts are explained through small pop-up windows that open when needed, providing users with additional context. The questions presented depend on previous answers, tailoring the assessment to the specific circumstances of the user's AI system. The results are displayed as a spider diagram, alongside a list of recommended actions for areas that require improvement. However, the weighting or contribution of each question to the final scores is not made clear to the user, nor is it explained how text-based answers are integrated into the tool (Radclyffe et al., 2023).

Building on this foundation, D2.3 offered a detailed examination of the seven requirements outlined in the ALTAI self-evaluation and established the conceptual framework for this deliverable, which primarily presents insights from the first iteration of the ALTAI self-evaluation conducted by ULEID. The Debiaser, which is designed to identify and mitigate diversity bias in AI systems for recruitment and selection, ultimately contributes to the broader development and deployment of AI in the workplace. While this presents significant opportunities to advance diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness, it is equally important to ensure that these goals are achieved in compliance with all relevant ethical requirements for trustworthy AI. Additionally, it is essential to assess whether the consequences of the Debiaser development and application have been fully considered and whether they align with the intended outcomes. In this context, the ALTAI self-evaluation serves as a vital tool, enabling the BIAS Consortium—particularly its technical partners—to make informed decisions about the future trajectory of the Debiaser. Furthermore, it provides a framework for reflecting on key factors related to the tool’s potential validation and commercialisation beyond the project's conclusion, as discussed in WP6. By using the ALTAI, stakeholders can address uncertainties surrounding ethical concerns and technological risks, which will be pivotal as the Debiaser progresses beyond its proof-of-concept phase.

4 Stakeholder engagement in the ALTAI performance

The performance of the ALTAI self-evaluation encourages AI developers to engage with a broad spectrum of stakeholders, fostering a more nuanced understanding of the challenges and solutions associated with technological innovation. Given that the framework is generic and lacks specific applicability, ULEID involved stakeholders inside and outside the BIAS Consortium to gather diverse perspectives, opinions, and attitudes towards the development of the ALTAI on the ongoing design of the Debiaser.

The engagement and brainstorming sessions, which focused on how different stakeholders interpreted the ALTAI requirements in the context of the future development of the Debiaser, were held during the co-creation workshops with external stakeholders throughout 2023, as well as the Consortium meeting in May 2024,² which included all Advisory Board Members. Given the focus of the BIAS project, particular emphasis was placed on the principles of diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness.

In total, ULEID organized two stakeholder sessions for the kick-off of the ALTAI self-evaluation:

- The practicum on 'Law & AI' as part of the Advanced Master on Law and Digital Technologies at Leiden University, on 10-14 June 2024, where a representative from BFH was also present. The total number of participants was: 57;
- The summer school on 'Law & Language' sponsored by the Erasmus+, Blended Intensive Programme, at Pavia University, on 16-20 September 2024. The total number of participants was: 26.

In each of these settings, the ALTAI self-evaluation process was preceded by an explanation of the envisioned design of the Debiaser and a role-playing exercise to help participants become familiar with the use of AI systems in hiring, particularly in relation to fairness and transparency. All used materials are included in Annex I

The exercise began with participants reading a job description and selecting the ranking criteria they deemed most relevant for the position, such as previous experience, education, language skills, or other factors. Next, participants reviewed and ranked four job applicants' CVs based on their relevance to the job vacancy and engaged in group discussions to justify their choices. Following this, they inputted their selected criteria and rankings into a BIAS demo available at (<https://blackbox.biasproject.eu/>)—provided by BFH and DIGITOUCH—allowing the AI system to evaluate the candidates while incorporating human input. Finally, they compared their rankings with the AI-generated results to identify and analyse any discrepancies in fruitful and engaging discussions.

Building on their experience of how an AI system for selection and recruitment worked, participants completed a dedicated form, created by ULEID for this purpose, aligned with the questionnaire available on the official ALTAI platform. Rather than assessing the Debiaser itself, this served as a reflective exercise aimed at clarifying how each ALTAI requirement should be interpreted and upheld in the development of a trustworthy technology for recruitment and selection.

The following subsections summarise the key considerations identified for each ALTAI requirement, while also reflecting participants' recognition of their interconnections. Although they acknowledged that many

² For more information, see Deliverable 2.4 on the final report on co-creation methodologies and findings available at <https://www.biasproject.eu/public_report/final-report-on-co-creation-methodologies-and-findings/> accessed: 10 March 2025

of their responses depended on the specific characteristics of the AI systems—details they either lacked or that might vary between the envisioned design of the Debiaser and the BIAS demo—they nonetheless engaged with the ALTAI questions. Their responses, valuable despite these uncertainties, offer insightful perspectives, particularly regarding the interpretation and potential implementation of ALTAI requirements in the future design of the Debiaser and, more broadly, in AI systems for recruitment and selection aimed at mitigating diversity bias in the workplace.

4.1 Human agency and oversight

Participants first assessed the risk of the Debiaser negatively impacting human agency as *moderate*. To mitigate this risk, they recommended continuous human oversight, with a human-in-command approach as the most immediate safeguard.³ They also proposed additional measures to strengthen accountability.

To prevent overreliance on AI in recruitment and selection, participants suggested that the system should avoid providing an overall ranking of candidates. Instead, AI outputs should present individual scores for each recruitment and selection criterion separately. This would allow for a more granular presentation of information, ensuring that HR professionals retain decision-making authority by selecting which criteria to prioritise.

Training was identified as another critical safeguard, particularly for both AI developers and HR practitioners, to enhance their understanding of AI functionality and potential risks to fundamental rights and principles.

Regarding mechanisms for detecting and responding to adverse effects, participants proposed several measures:

- Introducing a bias-aware criteria selection feature to flag potentially biased criteria;
- Enabling ex post human assessment of AI-generated results, with the option to re-run the AI;
- Establishing a bias objection mechanism, allowing job applicants to raise concerns through a dedicated feedback form or HR contact point;
- Conducting regular system audits to ensure ongoing fairness and transparency.

4.2 Technical robustness and safety

Participants widely acknowledged that AI systems for recruitment and selection—as well as, to some extent, technologies similar to the Debiaser—could pose safety risks, particularly when accuracy, reliability, and reproducibility are low. Although most participants did not have a background in computer science or related fields, they identified some key contexts, conditions, and processes to enhance technical robustness.

They suggested measures such as verifying data sources, conducting data audits, establishing key performance indicators, implementing incident reporting mechanisms, and conducting stress testing to address these risks. Additionally, they highlighted the importance of controlled experiments, simulation

³ Based on (AI HLEG, 2019), the levels of human involvement in this context include:

- Human-in-the-loop: Human intervention in each decision cycle of the AI application.
- Human-on-the-loop: Human involvement in designing AI applications and monitoring their functioning.
- Human-in-command: Continuous human intervention in both the design and use of the AI application.

environments, comprehensive logging, and independent verification and validation protocols to ensure system reliability and accountability.

4.3 Privacy and data governance

Participants identified a significant risk that any AI system used in recruitment and selection could infringe on the fundamental right to privacy and data protection, potentially triggering broader consequences for other fundamental rights and the overall well-being of job applicants. To mitigate this risk, ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU) 2016/679 was considered the most immediate safeguard, particularly given the Debiaser's bias identification and mitigation objectives.

Key GDPR provisions cited included the fundamental principles of data processing (Article 5) and the requirement to conduct a data protection impact assessment (Article 35), aligning with recommendations in the relevant literature (Rigotti & Fosch-Villaronga, 2024). Participants also raised concerns about the right to be forgotten (Article 17), highlighting the practical challenges of ensuring compliance. As a potential solution, they suggested that the AI system operate strictly locally to enhance data control. Additionally, participants emphasised the importance of aligning with international standards such as ISO/IEC 27701:2019 (Privacy Information Management) to strengthen compliance further.

4.4 Transparency

Compliance with transparency was examined across three key dimensions: traceability, explainability, and communication. Participants demonstrated clear and practical insights into how ALTAI compliance could be effectively implemented.

First, participants agreed that ensuring traceability requires continuous assessment of input data quality. They highlighted the importance of robust data governance measures, including:

- Data source verification and auditing mechanisms to ensure reliability.
- Documentation of data provenance to track the origins and transformations of data.
- Regular quality checks and validation protocols to prevent biases and inaccuracies from becoming embedded in the system.
- Comprehensive logging and independent verification for enhancing overall transparency and accountability.

Second, participants stressed the need for AI systems to be intuitive and accessible, ensuring that users can understand AI-generated explanations without requiring extensive technical knowledge. To achieve this, the system should:

- Use clear, non-technical language in all explanations.
- Communicate decisions step by step, specifying whether bias mitigation measures were applied.
- Employ visual aids such as charts and graphs to improve comprehension.

Third, effective communication was deemed crucial for transparency. Participants suggested that AI systems should:

- Provide contextual information about the data used, training processes, and employed algorithms.
- Regularly update users on system enhancements, particularly those improving fairness and performance.
- Use real-life case studies to demonstrate practical applications and fairness in decision-making.
- Communicate confidence levels of AI decisions and advise users to seek additional verification when uncertainty is high.

Fourth, participants acknowledged the challenges of evaluating whether users truly understand AI-generated decisions. They proposed various methods:

- Integrated feedback mechanisms (e.g., system prompts like “Did you understand this decision?”). However, excessive prompts could frustrate users and may not accurately reflect comprehension.
- Surveys and interviews to collect insights on user experiences, though these may lack immediacy and require significant resources.
- User testing and behavioural analytics to observe interactions and detect misunderstandings that structured surveys might miss. However, observer effects could distort real usage patterns.
- Diversity considerations to ensure feedback mechanisms capture perspectives from varied demographics while mitigating response bias.

Finally, participants emphasised that transparency efforts should span all interaction phases—before, during, and after AI use. They recommended employing multiple communication methods (textual, visual, and audio) and ensuring continuous access to transparency reports, feedback mechanisms, and FAQs.

4.5 Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness

While participants recognised the Debiaser as a potential tool for ‘avoiding unfair bias’—as defined in the ALTAI self-evaluation—they proposed additional measures to ensure its design and deployment adequately reflect diversity considerations.

To enhance inclusivity, they recommended testing and piloting the Debiaser with a diverse group of HR practitioners, including individuals from the disabled community, under the supervision of AI developers. This would facilitate direct exchange between users and developers, helping to balance user-centred and universal design principles more effectively.

However, participants also emphasised that AI developers should receive training on diversity-related needs, expectations, and risks—not only in relation to the Debiaser but also to AI technologies more

broadly. This training should adopt an intersectional perspective to ensure that multiple dimensions of identity and experience are considered.

To establish a robust mechanism for identifying and addressing bias, discrimination, or poor performance, participants suggested developing an intuitive and accessible reporting interface with clear guidelines. This should:

- Allow for anonymous reporting to encourage open feedback.
- Include a structured feedback loop that keeps users informed about the status and resolution of their reports.

4.6 Societal and environmental well-being

Participants lacked sufficient information to directly assess the environmental impact of the Debiaser or similar technologies, such as the BIAS Demo. However, they acknowledged potential risks and suggested monitoring measures to mitigate them. These included:

- Implementing a carbon footprint calculator to track environmental impact.
- Establishing sustainability metrics and reporting systems.
- Ensuring compliance with existing environmental certifications and standards.

Regarding the broader implications of automation in HR practices, participants focused primarily on AI systems similar to the BIAS Demo, as they perceived these to pose greater risks than the Debiaser. In line with relevant research, they recognised that AI could enhance efficiency and support human decision-making. However, they also raised concerns about:

- Job displacement in HR due to automation.
- The risk of deskilling, where HR professionals may become overly reliant on AI, diminishing their expertise over time.

4.7 Accountability

Participants viewed accountability as requiring robust mechanisms to ensure transparency, oversight, and trustworthiness in AI systems. They emphasised that auditors must have sufficient access to examine how AI functions, which demands transparency across the entire development lifecycle.

To achieve this, they identified key measures, including:

- Enhanced traceability through version control and documentation.
- Comprehensive logging of system processes and outcomes.
- Audit-friendly infrastructure that provides secure, read-only access to relevant data.

However, participants stressed that accountability should not be limited to technical measures. Instead, it should be reinforced through external oversight, including third-party audits and independent review bodies. They also highlighted the importance of clear reporting mechanisms allowing users to flag potential biases or issues, with structured feedback loops ensuring transparency in addressing concerns.

Finally, participants underscored that accountability must be rooted in legal and ethical frameworks, particularly through compliance with regulatory standards such as the EU AI Act.

4.8 Stakeholder insights and their integration

The responses of external stakeholders, despite uncertainties regarding technical details, were expected to offer valuable insights—particularly concerning the interpretation and potential implementation of ALTAI requirements in the future design of the Debiaser and, more broadly, in AI systems for recruitment and selection aimed at mitigating diversity bias in the workplace. While BFH and NTNU participated in all brainstorming sessions in Venice and Porto, BFH also attended the first stakeholder engagement in Leiden. In contrast, ULEID conducted the ALTAI self-evaluation independently in Pavia, later reporting back to BFH and NTNU.

These findings provided BFH and NTNU with a deeper understanding of how diverse stakeholders interpret ALTAI requirements in the context of AI in the labour market—requirements that are often ambiguous and open to multiple interpretations. While the BIAS Consortium had previously engaged in discussions on these topics, particularly the ‘diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness’ requirement, the ALTAI self-evaluation allowed them to refine their perspective by offering additional insights on these complex themes. Both Consortium and WP3 meetings served as ideal platforms for facilitating these discussions and integrating a wide range of viewpoints.

Beyond theoretical considerations, ULEID, BFH, and NTNU actively integrated specific stakeholder recommendations, particularly as they anticipate the Debiaser moving beyond its proof-of-concept stage. This process of integration is evident in several key areas, where the stakeholder responses were either directly incorporated into the development or aligned with the recommendations provided by ULEID and the ALTAI platform. For example, stakeholders emphasised the need for training AI developers and HR practitioners to improve their understanding of AI functionality and mitigate potential risks, particularly around human autonomy, oversight, and societal well-being. The BIAS Consortium is already actively engaged in this effort through capacity-building sessions and an e-learning course as part of WP5. Additionally, the integration of GDPR compliance was strengthened, aligning the stakeholders’ concerns with BFH and NTNU’s ongoing efforts to ensure robust data protection practices. In terms of transparency and environmental well-being, BFH and NTNU acknowledged the stakeholders’ practical suggestions but noted that these considerations remain premature, given the early-stage development of the NLP and CBR modules. As the BIAS project evolves, these concerns will be revisited to ensure alignment with the stakeholders’ expectations. Similarly, while testing and piloting the Debiaser with a diverse group of HR practitioners appears feasible in the future, BFH and NTNU have already incorporated an intersectional perspective into their work. This commitment is exemplified by the publication ‘*A Systematic Review of Bias Detection Methods for Non-English Word Embeddings and Language Models*’ in *Artificial Intelligence Review*, which highlights cross-disciplinary collaboration within the BIAS Consortium and underscores their commitment to diversity and inclusivity. Finally, with respect to accountability, the insights from ULEID and the self-evaluation results generated by the ALTAI platform were aligned with the stakeholders’ recommendation that external auditing could add value in the future. This recommendation is being taken into account for future iterations of the Debiaser, particularly as the project progresses toward commercialisation. External, independent auditing is seen as a critical step in ensuring the long-term credibility and accountability of the Debiaser from a commercial exploitation perspective. By incorporating independent evaluations, DIGI aims to enhance trust among users and demonstrate a commitment to ethical AI practices, particularly in sensitive applications like recruitment and selection. As the Debiaser will transition from its proof-of-concept stage to a market-ready solution, such measures

will play a pivotal role in fostering transparency and building confidence among HR practitioners, organisations, and other end-users. Ultimately, this approach underscores the BIAS Consortium's dedication to creating an AI tool that adheres to the highest standards of fairness, accountability, and inclusivity.

5 ALTAI first iteration

In December 2024, ULEID provided BFH and NTNU with instructions for conducting the first iteration of the ALTAI self-evaluation, following an agreement that this timing would best balance the Consortium Agreement deadline with the design process of the Debiaser. To facilitate the process, ULEID created a dedicated account on the official ALTAI website and requested BFH and NTNU to complete a 'MyALTAI' form for each NLP and CBR tool they were developing, enabling subsequent multidisciplinary discussion and analysis.

The initial plan was to share and discuss the findings during a dedicated WP3 meeting in January 2025. However, BFH and NTNU identified key challenges in conducting the ALTAI self-evaluation. Specifically, they recognised that:

- The NLP tools did not fully meet the ALTAI definition of AI systems.
- The CBR module was still in its early design stage, making it difficult to provide meaningful responses to all ALTAI questions.

ULEID, BFH, and NTNU decided to partially conduct the ALTAI self-evaluation for the NLP tools outside the official platform to address these limitations. This approach allowed for a more detailed explanation of how each tool aligns (or does not align) with the ALTAI definitions, and refined responses in cases where the standard closed-answer format of the self-evaluation did not adequately capture necessary nuances. The official platform was used for the CBR tool. The response option 'don't know' was selected when questions could not be answered due to the early stage of the design process.

The following analysis presents the outcomes of this process, constituting the first iteration of the ALTAI self-evaluation for the Debiaser.

5.1 NLP-1

NLP-1 aims at detecting and mitigating bias in word embeddings and language models in the different consortium languages. For this, different methods from the state-of-the-art (WEAT, SEAT, etc.) are implemented, and specific word and sentence lists derived from co-creation activities have been created for Dutch, German, Icelandic, Italian, Norwegian and Turkish. The module consists of a suite of tests that can be applied to existing pre-trained models (e.g., fasttext embeddings, BERT and GPT models) or custom models using similar infrastructures (e.g. HuggingFace). In the second half of the project, the mitigation part will be implemented, and methods will be extended to black-box LLMs, where direct access to the embeddings and model weights is not possible, and the only interaction occurs via prompting.

The system analyzes and modifies word embeddings and therefore does not process personal data or make decisions about humans. This should help AI developers to introduce less bias in their systems. Its impact on society is that it can reduce bias in other AI systems.

AI developers will use this technology to test existing models (or their own models) for societal stereotypes and/or to reduce the bias within those systems. The aim of the tools when being used within the intended use is to reduce bias in the AI tools using the pre-trained models.

More details about the technical implementation and results of this software component can be found in the Deliverables 3.1 and 3.2 - Preliminary Versions.

5.1.1 ALTAI definition for NLP-1

Based on the definition provided on the ALTAI platform,

“Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal. AI systems can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and they can also adapt their behaviour by analysing how the environment is affected by their previous actions. As a scientific discipline, AI includes several approaches and techniques, such as machine learning (of which deep learning and reinforcement learning are specific examples), machine reasoning (which includes planning, scheduling, knowledge representation and reasoning, search, and optimization), and robotics (which includes control, perception, sensors and actuators, as well as the integration of all other techniques into cyber-physical systems).

According to BFH, the definition provided on the ALTAI platform is quite broad, and only the initial part can be considered applicable to the first NLP tool developed within the BIAS project. This tool automates statistical test computations, relying on predefined word lists derived from the project's research outcomes. Unlike AI systems that adapt their behaviour by analysing environmental changes based on previous actions, these tools operate in a strictly deterministic manner. Each script execution produces the same results, independent of prior runs. Furthermore, they do not incorporate machine learning or machine reasoning, which are key elements outlined in the ALTAI definition.

5.1.2 Agency and human oversight for NLP-1

The first question in the *Human Agency and Oversight* section of the ALTAI self-evaluation asks: “Is the AI system designed to interact with, guide, or make decisions for human end-users that affect individuals or society?” The response is negative in this case, as NLP-1 is not designed to make decisions human users. Instead, it serves as a tool for testing existing models for societal stereotypes and mitigating bias within those systems, with the potential to guide end-users in this process to some extent.

Following this, the self-evaluation inquires about the degree of human involvement and oversight in the AI system, offering options such as fully autonomous, human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, and human-in-command. Initially, none of these categories seem to fully capture the role of NLP-1. The most fitting response would likely be “other” or “not applicable,” as the tool operates deterministically and is designed primarily for AI developers to assess and mitigate diversity bias in pre-trained language models and word embeddings. Rather than engaging directly with end-users, NLP-1 functions as a diagnostic tool in the development phase of AI systems, which may later be integrated into software applications. However, despite its diagnostic nature, the final decision on how to address any identified bias lies with the developers. As they interact with the tool and make the final call on how to apply its findings, it could be described as a “human-in-command” tool. Nonetheless, it is essential to recognise that NLP-1 does not make decisions itself; it simply provides developers with insights into potential biases that inform the decision-making process, supporting future system design and auditing efforts.

Lastly, even though NLP-1 is not a decision-making system, there remains a potential risk of misinterpretation or overreliance — for instance, if its outputs are taken as definitive assessments of fairness without critical contextualisation. It is therefore important to clearly communicate the tool's

scope and limitations to avoid misleading assumptions about its role or authority in shaping final AI deployments.

5.1.3 Technical robustness and safety for NLP-1

In the *Technical Robustness and Safety* section, the first question asks whether the AI system is certified for cybersecurity or complies with relevant security standards. The response is negative, and the BIAS Consortium does not plan to pursue such certification by the end of the project. This decision is based on the fact that NLP-1 is a proof-of-concept rather than a fully developed application, meaning that it will not reach a stage of maturity where certification would be relevant.

Subsequently, the ALTAI self-evaluation inquires whether:

- The AI system could have adverse, critical, or damaging effects (e.g., on human or societal safety) due to risks such as design flaws, technical faults, outages, attacks, misuse, or malicious use.
- A low level of accuracy could lead to adverse, critical, or damaging consequences.
- Due to its low reliability and/or reproducibility, the AI system could cause adverse, critical, or damaging consequences.

None of these questions apply to NLP-1, as it is only a proof-of-concept. Additionally, its purpose is to assist AI developers in assessing bias within pre-trained language models, rather than making autonomous decisions or directly impacting individuals or society.

When addressing accuracy, the ALTAI self-evaluation also asks for a self-assessment of the risk that accuracy may drop below an intended level and the measures taken to address this. However, NLP-1 does not align with conventional notions of ‘accuracy’ in machine learning models since it does not rely on predictive algorithms or decision-making processes. In this context, a potential interpretation of ‘low accuracy’ would be failing to detect bias when it is present. By design, NLP-1 has known blind spots and captures only a subset of biases identified in the co-creation process.⁴ Nonetheless, even in the least effective scenario—where only a small fraction of bias is detected and mitigated—the tool would still provide value.

Moreover, the self-evaluation asks whether the AI system employs online continual learning, which is not applicable to NLP-1. It also requests a reliability rating, which BFH considers moderate, expecting improvement following validation. The adopted measures to ensure reliability are deemed adequate based on well-established scientific methods.

The section concludes with three questions regarding reproducibility and fallback mechanisms. In this regard, the reproducibility of NLP-1 is rated as high, and the adopted measures are considered appropriate, given that experiments can be replicated using the same dataset, methodology, and statistical tests implemented in the tool.

5.1.4 Privacy and data governance for NLP-1

The NLP-1 tool does not process personal data and, therefore, the GDPR does not apply. Privacy and Data Governance section begins by asking whether the AI developer has considered the impact of the AI system

⁴ For more details see: <<https://www.biasproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/BIAS-D2.4-Final-Submitted.pdf>> accessed: 10 March 2025

on the right to privacy, physical, mental, and moral integrity, and data protection. BFH and the BIAS Consortium has undertaken this assessment as documented in Deliverable 2.1 and, more specifically, the data protection management plan of the BIAS project.⁵

Subsequently, the ALTAI self-evaluation includes several questions on data governance. However, these are not applicable to NLP-1, as the tool does not process personal data. Instead, it relies solely on resources generated within the BIAS project, which will be made publicly available, as well as publicly available pre-trained word embeddings and language models.

5.1.5 Transparency for NLP-1

In the *Transparency* section, the ALTAI self-evaluation first examines the AI system's traceability, specifically whether measures have been implemented to assess the quality of input data continuously. This question does not apply to NLP-1, as each software execution is entirely independent of previous runs. The tool does not involve continuous learning or iterative data processing.

Regarding the mandatory question of whether the AI system's decisions are explained to users, this is again not entirely relevant to NLP-1. The tool does not operate as a decision-making system but rather as a deterministic implementation of statistical tests. Its source code and formulas are openly available, eliminating concerns about opacity or black-box mechanisms. Similarly, when asked about the continuous surveying of users to assess their understanding of the AI system's decisions, the response is complex. While user awareness and comprehension could be enhanced through targeted sensitisation efforts, this would be more relevant at a later stage, potentially during the commercialisation process, rather than in the current research proof-of-concept phase of the BIAS project.

5.1.6 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness for NLP-1

In the *Diversity, Non-Discrimination, and Fairness* section, the ALTAI self-evaluation first asks whether a strategy or set of procedures has been established to prevent the creation or reinforcement of unfair bias in the AI system, both in terms of input data and algorithmic design. In the case of NLP-1, a simple yes/no answer is not possible, as the tool itself is designed to detect and mitigate bias in other AI applications, rather than being an AI system requiring bias mitigation. It could be argued that the selection of bias detection word and sentence lists is inherently shaped by the research decisions made within the BIAS project (e.g., the use case selection in co-creation workshops within WP2). One recognised limitation of the implemented approach is that the bias detection word and sentence lists currently cover only a specific subset of biases, primarily focusing on gender and race. This limitation stems from the nature of state-of-the-art methods and the inherent complexity of bias detection. However, it is important to note that this approach does not align with the classical notion of 'unwanted bias' in machine learning, as NLP-1 does not rely on black-box mechanisms such as deep learning. Instead, it is a fully explainable tool, employing transparent statistical methods with openly accessible source code. Moreover, this represents only the starting point within the BIAS project, as the tool will be further expanded over time. Given its open-source nature, other researchers will have the opportunity to contribute, enhancing its scope and effectiveness in the long term.

The self-evaluation then asks whether the AI system is designed to accommodate a variety of preferences and abilities in society. While this could be considered at a later stage, particularly during

⁵ Deliverable 2.1 is available at: <<https://www.biasproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/BIAS-D2.1-FINAL-SUBMITTED.pdf>> accessed: 10 March 2025

commercialisation, it is not directly relevant to the current proof-of-concept. Any such considerations would likely focus on the graphical user interface (GUI), including aspects such as accessibility, colour schemes, and font sizes, in line with standard IT development practices. Conversely, when asked whether mechanisms were implemented to engage with diverse stakeholders in the AI system's design process, the answer is affirmative. Co-creation has been a core pillar of the BIAS project, and the participatory process shaping the Debiaser, including NLP-1, is fully documented in Deliverables 2.2 and 2.4. However, for the sake of clarity, it is important to note that no tests with potential users have been conducted thus far.

5.1.7 Societal and environmental well-being for NLP-1

Regarding the potential environmental impact of the NLP-1 tool, as addressed at the beginning of the *Environment and Societal Well-being* section, the response is negative. While it is still early in the development stage to accurately quantify energy consumption or carbon footprint, the tool does not rely on deep learning or other computationally intensive models. It can be executed on standard computers without the need for specialised compute resources such as GPUs, meaning its energy consumption and carbon footprint are negligible, and it does not raise significant environmental concerns.

Similarly, the response is also negative when assessing the potential impact of NLP-1 on work and work arrangements and the risk of deskilling the workforce. NLP-1 is intended for AI developers and will be integrated into existing software development processes without any foreseeable impact on employment structures. Moreover, WP5 includes dedicated activities for educational purposes, further supporting knowledge dissemination rather than replacing human expertise.

5.1.8 Accountability for NLP-1

In the *Accountability* section, the first question concerns the establishment of mechanisms to facilitate the auditability of the AI system, such as traceability of the development process, sourcing of training data, and logging of the system's processes, outcomes, and impact (both positive and negative). In the case of NLP-1, the tool is fully transparent, with all resources being open-source. Moreover, no training data is involved, as the tool does not rely on machine learning.

The question is not applicable when asked whether external guidance or third-party auditing processes are foreseen to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures, as NLP-1 is a deterministic tool that does not make autonomous decisions or learn from data. Nonetheless, ULEID is in contact with the Next Generation EU project 'IA+Igal', which focuses on AI auditing, including in workplace contexts,⁶ should such a necessity arise in the future. Additionally, BFH envisions a potential use of NLP-1 for auditing purposes.

5.1.9 ALTAI results and recommendations for NLP-1

As the official ALTAI platform typically provides tailored results and recommendations upon completing the self-evaluation, ULEID has independently developed the following considerations. Although the NLP-1 tool may not fully align with ALTAI's definition of an AI system, ensuring its development follows trustworthy AI principles remains valuable.

⁶ More information are available at <<https://iamasigual.eu/en/>> accessed: 24.02.2025

Table 2: ALTAI results and recommendations for NLP-1

ALTAI Requirement	Findings	Recommendations
Human agency and oversight	NLP-1 functions as a bias detection tool, not a decision-making system, but there is a risk of misinterpretation or overreliance.	Provide clear user guidance stating NLP-1's role and limitations. If NLP-1 evolves beyond proof-of-concept, consider external validation for effectiveness, security, and safety.
Technical robustness and safety	NLP-1 is a proof-of-concept and not a fully developed AI application. It currently lacks security measures, validation, and stress-testing mechanisms.	If further developed, introduce security measures, validation protocols, and stress-testing mechanisms. Future iterations could benefit from compliance with relevant security standards.
Transparency	The source code and formulas of NLP-1 are openly available, ensuring transparency. Since each execution is independent of previous runs, continuous data quality assessment is not applicable.	Provide user-friendly documentation and tutorials to support AI developers. Offer accessible explanations of statistical methods.
Privacy and data governance	NLP-1 does not process personal data, resulting in minimal privacy risks.	Maintain awareness of privacy and data governance standards to ensure ongoing compliance.
Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness	NLP-1 was developed through co-creation activities that ensured inclusivity.	Future adaptations should consider additional accessibility enhancements, especially for commercial applications.
Societal and environmental well-being	NLP-1 has a lightweight computational footprint and is resource-efficient.	Maintain NLP-1's low environmental impact to support sustainability.
Accountability	NLP-1 follows a transparent development process and offers open-source access, but	Continue ensuring transparency and open access. Future applications in AI fairness

	external auditing is not currently in place.	evaluations could benefit from third-party oversight or collaboration with relevant initiatives.
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5.2 NLP-2

This NLP-2 module builds on the research conducted on cover letters, as detailed in Deliverable 3.2. The findings currently suggest two potential directions for a tool, outlined below. These are preliminary results and may be subject to further refinement:

- A framework for using machine learning classifiers to examine existing datasets for potential biases. This method has been applied to datasets that cannot be shared, meaning it is designed to be implemented on custom datasets provided by potential users.
- A library of keywords and tools for analysing textual data. This tool highlights sensitive words or proxies that could introduce biases when integrated into external HR tools used by customers (not tools developed within the BIAS project).

The framework is intended for use by HR officers, AI developers, and other interested stakeholders to assess potential biases or words that could lead to bias in textual data—particularly in cover letters and potentially CV data—before feeding this data into third-party black-box AI systems.

The intended use cases for these tools differ:

- The machine learning framework (1) is designed for users working with large datasets rather than individual documents. Those applying this framework would replicate the bias detection methods developed in BIAS on their own datasets.
- The keyword-based tool (2) can be applied at the individual document level. HR professionals and job applicants can use it to identify words/phrases that could lead to diversity bias in a cover letter and take steps to mitigate this potential effect.

More details about the technical implementation and results from first practical experiments with real-world data is included in Deliverable D3.2.

5.2.1 ALTAI definition for NLP-2

Based on the definition provided on the ALTAI platform,

“Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal. AI systems can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and they can also adapt their behaviour by analysing how the environment is affected by their previous actions. As a scientific discipline, AI includes several approaches and techniques, such as machine learning (of which deep learning and reinforcement learning are specific examples), machine reasoning (which includes planning, scheduling, knowledge representation and reasoning, search, and optimization), and robotics (which includes control, perception, sensors and actuators, as well as the integration of all other techniques into cyber-physical systems).

However, some clarifications are necessary, as the ALTAI definition does not fully align with the NLP-2 tool. Notably,

- For the machine learning framework (1): Machine learning is employed, but the solution does not provide a pre-trained model (i.e., it does not involve training data). Instead, it offers a framework and methods, enabling users to apply their own data to conduct machine learning analyses and examine the results. The objective is not decision-making but rather assessing the degree of bias within a system.
- For the keyword-based tool (2): The ALTAI definition refers to “a complex goal”, but this characterisation does not fully apply here. The tool’s value lies not in complexity, but in the knowledge derived from qualitative tasks—specifically, existing literature, co-creation activities and focus groups conducted within BIAS. The tool is reproducible, deterministic, and designed to identify relevant words in a text. Its underlying methodology is primarily rule-based NLP, rather than machine learning or machine reasoning. No training data, machine learning, or robotics are involved. However, some pre-trained models or libraries (e.g., for stemming or lemmatisation) may be used to perform linguistic processing tasks.

5.2.2 Human agency and oversight for NLP-2

The *Human Agency and Oversight* section begins by examining whether the AI system is designed to interact with, guide, or make decisions on behalf of human end-users that impact individuals or society. In this case, the response is negative, unless the NLP-2 tool is extensively considered. As was the case with NLP-1, the final decision on how to address any identified bias remains with the developers. Since they interact with the tool and ultimately determine how to apply its findings, it may be more accurately described as a “human-in-command” tool.

As a result, the self-evaluation shifts to whether procedures have been established to prevent user overreliance and safeguard human autonomy. The primary concern identified by BFH is the risk of users placing excessive trust in the application. While the system can highlight certain biases and track progress in mitigating them, it cannot guarantee the detection of all potential biases. There is a risk that users may misinterpret the tool’s output as definitive, leading to the erroneous assumption that the system itself is free of bias—a notion that does not align with reality. To address this, the final proof-of-concept will explicitly communicate these limitations.

The ALTAI self-evaluation further inquires about human involvement and oversight in the AI system. Given that the NLP-2 tool is used solely by individuals assessing their datasets for bias, its operation remains entirely within human control, with no automated decision-making or autonomous interventions affecting users or society.

5.2.3 Technical robustness and safety for NLP-2

The Technical Robustness and Safety section begins by examining whether the AI system is certified for cybersecurity or complies with relevant security standards. As with the NLP-1 tool, the response is negative, and the BIAS Consortium does not intend to pursue such certification by the end of the project. This decision is based on the fact that NLP-2 remains a proof-of-concept rather than a fully developed application, meaning that it will not reach a level of maturity where certification would be relevant.

The ALTAI self-evaluation subsequently inquires whether the AI system:

- Poses risks of adverse, critical, or damaging effects (e.g., on human or societal safety) due to design flaws, technical faults, outages, attacks, misuse, or malicious use.
- Could cause harm due to a low level of accuracy.
- Might lead to adverse consequences resulting from low reliability and/or reproducibility.

None of these concerns are applicable to NLP-2, as it remains a proof-of-concept.

Regarding accuracy, the self-evaluation asks for a self-assessment of the risk that accuracy may drop below an intended level and the measures taken to address this. However, given that NLP-2 is designed to support bias detection, even a partial identification of biases enhances the system's effectiveness. For instance, even if only 1% of biases are detected, the system still provides value. Consequently, a lack of absolute accuracy does not constitute a specific harm in this context.

Additionally, the ALTAI self-evaluation asks whether the AI system employs online continual learning, which is not applicable to NLP-2. It also requires a reliability rating, which BFH currently considers moderate, with expectations of improvement following validation. The adopted measures to ensure reliability are deemed adequate, as the approach prioritises explainability—for instance, using LIME as an explainer for machine learning. Moreover, keyword-based approaches are inherently explainable and transparent by design.

The section concludes with three questions concerning reproducibility and fallback mechanisms. At this stage, NLP-2's results are explainable and reproducible based on the current understanding of its implementation.

5.2.4 Privacy and data governance for NLP-2

The *Privacy and Data Governance* section begins by examining whether the AI developer has considered the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, physical, mental, and moral integrity, and data protection. This assessment has been conducted by BFH and, more broadly, by the BIAS Consortium, as previously said and documented in Deliverable 2.1.

The ALTAI self-evaluation subsequently poses several questions on data governance. However, these are not applicable to NLP-2 at this stage, as it remains a proof-of-concept. The relevance of data governance will depend on the practical application of the tool. In practice, the type of data processed is determined by the user, who may choose to input either personal or anonymised data. Importantly, personal data is not required for the correct functioning of the framework or the tool.

5.2.5 Transparency for NLP-2

For the self-evaluation of the *Transparency* requirement, the ALTAI first inquires about the implementation of measures to continuously assess the quality of input data for the AI system. The response is affirmative, as the NLP-2 tool itself serves as a measure to assess data before it is transferred to other AI systems.

Regarding whether the AI system's decisions are explained to users and whether users are continuously surveyed to assess their understanding, the answer remains uncertain at this stage. The outputs of NLP-2 are, to some extent, explainable, particularly through the use of LIME explainability libraries. These explanations can be made available to users, but the precise method and extent of implementation will

be determined in the post-validation phase, when the proof-of-concept is further developed into a product. Technically, explainability is feasible, but its integration into the user interface requires further consideration.

Finally, any remaining questions concerning transparency and human-machine interaction are not applicable, as the NLP-2 tool is exclusively used by individuals assessing their datasets for bias, with its operation fully under human control.

5.2.6 Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness for NLP-2

In the *Diversity, Non-Discrimination, and Fairness* section, the ALTAI self-evaluation first inquires whether a strategy or set of procedures has been established to prevent the creation or reinforcement of unfair bias within the AI system, considering both input data and algorithmic design. In the case of NLP-2, a straightforward yes/no answer is not applicable, as the tool itself is designed to detect and mitigate bias in other AI applications, rather than being an AI system that requires its own bias mitigation measures.

The self-evaluation then asks whether the AI system is designed to accommodate a variety of preferences and abilities in society. For BFH, this primarily concerns usability, which is expected to be addressed at a later stage—potentially after the completion of the BIAS project—when the proof-of-concept is further developed into a product.

Conversely, when asked whether mechanisms have been implemented to engage with diverse stakeholders in the AI system’s design process, the response is affirmative. Co-creation has been a central pillar of the BIAS project, and the participatory process shaping the Debiaser, including NLP-2, is comprehensively documented in Deliverables 2.2 and 2.4.

5.2.7 Societal and environmental well-being for NLP-2

Regarding the potential environmental impact of the NLP-2 tool, as addressed in the Environment and Societal Well-being section, the response is negative. However, it may be worth estimating the CO₂ emissions of the system when operating in a production-near environment. While not expected to be extremely high, this assessment could be particularly relevant for the machine learning component used to investigate bias in datasets, that might potentially make use of GPU compute resources. Examining the cost-benefit trade-off in this context could provide valuable insights.

Similarly, when evaluating the potential impact of NLP-2 on work and work arrangements, as well as the risk of workforce deskilling, the response is also negative. NLP-2 is designed as a tool for HR professionals, assisting them in identifying bias risks when using other automated systems. It is not expected to fundamentally alter their work processes or contribute to deskilling. On the contrary, one could argue that NLP-2 supports upskilling, as it raises awareness of bias and equips professionals with better tools for identifying and addressing it.

5.2.8 Accountability for NLP-2

In the *Accountability* section, the first question concerns the establishment of mechanisms to facilitate auditability in the AI system, including traceability of the development process, sourcing of training data, and logging of system processes, outcomes, and impact (both positive and negative). In the case of NLP-2, some data—such as sensitive and proxy words in texts—is sourced from validated research within the BIAS project. The remaining data consists of the client’s own data, meaning that its content and origins

are fully transparent to the client. The methods used in NLP-2—such as word dictionaries, similarity analysis, and traditional machine learning with explainable AI libraries—ensure that its processes are generally explainable and transparent. However, logging mechanisms would need to be implemented at the product stage, as they are not yet included in the proof-of-concept.

Regarding external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures, the question is not applicable to NLP-2. As a deterministic tool, NLP-2 does not make autonomous decisions or learn from data. Nonetheless, ULEID is in contact with the Next Generation EU project ‘IA+Iqual’, which focuses on AI auditing, including in workplace contexts. Should the need for external auditing arise in the future, this collaboration may offer relevant insights. Additionally, BFH envisions a potential use of NLP-1 for auditing purposes.

5.2.9 ALTAI results and recommendations for NLP-2

As previously said, since the official ALTAI platform typically provides tailored results and recommendations following a self-evaluation, ULEID has developed the following considerations for NLP-2. Although NLP-2 may not fully align with ALTAI’s definition of an AI system, ensuring a trustworthy design remains essential.

Table 3 ALTAI results and recommendations for NLP-2

ALTAI Requirement	Findings	Recommendations
Human agency and oversight	NLP-2 does not guide, make decisions for, or interact with human end-users in ways that impact individuals or society. However, user overreliance remains a risk. NLP-2 highlights biases but cannot detect all possible biases.	Develop clear guidance to ensure users understand that NLP-2 is a bias detection tool rather than a decision-making system. Explicitly communicate its limitations. If NLP-2 progresses beyond the proof-of-concept stage, external validation should be considered to assess its effectiveness, security, and safety.
Technical robustness and safety	NLP-2 is a proof-of-concept and is not certified for cybersecurity. The BIAS Consortium does not plan to pursue certification before the project's conclusion. Its reliability is considered moderate, with improvements expected following validation. Since NLP-2 does not employ predictive models or online continual learning, conventional	Future iterations could undergo targeted performance evaluations to assess bias detection effectiveness. Ensure reproducibility by maintaining explainability and using consistent datasets and methodologies.

	accuracy assessments do not apply.	
Privacy and data governance	NLP-2 does not process personal data (unless provided by the users), relying solely on resources generated within the BIAS project and standard models. This minimises privacy risks. However, awareness of data governance remains crucial.	If NLP-2 were to be integrated into a broader system, future iterations should provide clear guidance on data handling practices, particularly if users choose to input personal or sensitive data.
Transparency	NLP-2 serves as a tool for assessing data before integration into other AI systems, but user understanding could be improved. Non-expert users may find its statistical methods difficult to interpret.	Provide user-friendly documentation or tutorials to support HR practitioners and AI developers in applying NLP-2's findings effectively. Offer accessible explanations of NLP-2's statistical methods. Future iterations should explore integrating explainability features into the user interface.
Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness	NLP-2 is designed to detect and mitigate bias rather than requiring its own bias mitigation. However, usability considerations remain relevant, particularly regarding accessibility for diverse users. The participatory co-creation approach followed in the BIAS project ensures inclusivity.	Enhance accessibility in future applications, particularly if NLP-2 is commercialised. Maintain participatory approaches to ensure inclusivity.
Societal and environmental well-being	NLP-2 does not employ particularly computationally intensive methods, resulting in minimal environmental impact. However, estimating its CO ₂ emissions in a production-near environment could provide useful insights. While NLP-2 does not directly impact workforce dynamics, it plays a	Consider estimating NLP-2's CO ₂ emissions to assess the trade-off between computational cost and bias detection performance. Emphasise its contribution to upskilling HR practitioners and AI developers.

	role in upskilling HR practitioners and AI developers.	
Accountability	NLP-2 follows a transparent approach, making use of explainable AI methods or natively explainable approaches. Logging mechanisms are not yet in place, as external audits are not currently applicable. However, BFH envisions a potential future role for NLP-2 in auditing.	If NLP-2 is further developed, implement logging mechanisms to ensure accountability. Maintain engagement with AI auditing initiatives to gather insights for potential external validation. Explore BFH's envisioned use of NLP-2 for auditing purposes.

5.3 CBR

CBR serves as the foundational AI approach for the proposed Decision Support System (DSS). This system is designed to assist HR practitioners during the initial candidate screening process, producing one of three possible outcomes for a candidate applying for a specific job opening: "Shortlist," "Longlist," or "Negative." These correspond to recruitment decisions as follows:

- "Shortlist" – The candidate is invited for an interview.
- "Longlist" – The candidate is placed on a backup list.
- "Negative" – The candidate is not considered further.

The core principle of CBR is that "similar problems or situations tend to have similar solutions or decisions." This aligns with a key fairness principle: "Individuals with similar characteristics should receive similar treatment." Accordingly, CBR leverages past experiences—particularly relevant historical cases—to inform present decisions. When evaluating a candidate for a given job, the system references previous decisions involving similar applicants to guide its assessment. A key advantage of CBR over mainstream machine learning approaches is its interpretability and transparency, as it does not function as a black-box model. Unlike purely data-driven approaches, CBR incorporates prior knowledge, making it a hybrid AI method.

The CBR system consists of three main components:

- The Case Base – A repository of past cases.
- Domain Knowledge – Context-specific expertise that informs similarity assessment.
- The CBR Engine – Uses an adapted version of the k-nearest neighbors (k-NN) algorithm, incorporating domain-specific similarity assessment to measure how closely a new applicant matches past cases.

CBR's domain-specific nature enables it to identify semantically similar cases, even when differences exist at a surface level. This is particularly relevant in recruitment, where candidates may express identical qualifications or experiences in different ways.

The similarity assessment process is transparent and involves calculating the weighted sum of distances between attributes in past cases and those in a new case. The weight assigned to each attribute reflects its importance, as determined by multiple HR experts. These weights are adjustable, allowing customization based on the company and job type. The DSS remains transparent by explicitly showing which past cases were used to inform a given decision.

From a fairness perspective, the system prioritizes "individual fairness" over "group fairness." By ensuring that similar individuals receive similar treatment, the CBR engine promotes consistency and procedural fairness, focusing not only on the outcome but also on the decision-making process itself.

5.3.1 ALTAI definition for CBR

Unlike the NLP-1 and NLP-2 tools, the CBR-based DSS fully aligns with the ALTAI definition of an AI system, making it suitable for evaluation using the ALTAI self-assessment tool. Furthermore, its advanced stage of development enables responses to most of the self-evaluation questions. Accordingly, NTNU successfully completed the self-evaluation on the official ALTAI platform. The following subsections outline its responses for each category, along with the overall official results.

5.3.2 Human autonomy and oversight for CBR

Human autonomy

Is the AI system designed to interact, guide or take decisions by human end-users that affect humans ('subjects') or society?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Could the AI system generate confusion for some or all end-users or subjects on whether a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision?

- Yes
- No

Could the AI system generate confusion for some or all end-users or subjects on whether they are interacting with a human or AI system?

- Yes
- No

Could the AI system affect human autonomy by generating over-reliance by end-users?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the (end-user's decision-making process in any other (unintended) way?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place any procedure to avoid that the system inadvertently affects human autonomy?

- Yes
- No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system negatively affects human autonomy?

- Non-existent
- Low
- Moderate
- Significant
- High

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to mitigate this risk?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system creates human attachment or addiction to the system or can be used in manipulative ways?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to mitigate this risk?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Human oversight

Please describe whether the AI system (tick as many as appropriate):

- Is a self-learning or autonomous system
- Is overseen by a human-in-the-loop
- Is overseen by a human-on-the-loop
- Is overseen by a human-in-command
- Other
- Don't know

Have the humans (human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, human-in-command) been given specific training on how to exercise oversight?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you establish any detection and response mechanisms for undesirable adverse effects of the AI system for the end-user or subject?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you ensure a "stop button" or procedure to safely abort an operation when needed?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the oversight procedures you have set up for the AI system?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

5.3.3 Technical robustness and safety for CBR

Security

Is the AI system certified for cybersecurity (e.g., the certification scheme created by the Cybersecurity Act in Europe) or is it compliant with specific security standards?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

General safety

Could the AI system have adversarial, critical or damaging effects (e.g., to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you define risk, risk metrics and risk levels of the AI system in each specific use case?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you identify the possible threats to the AI system (design faults, technical faults, environmental threats) and the possible resulting consequences?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you assess the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use of the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you define safety criticality levels (e.g., related to human integrity) of the possible consequences of faults or misuse of the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you assess the dependency of critical system's decisions on its stable and reliable behavior?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you align the reliability/testing requirements to the appropriate levels of stability and reliability?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you plan fault tolerance via, e.g., a duplicated system or another parallel system (AI-based or “conventional”)?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you develop a mechanism to evaluate when the AI system has been changed enough to merit a new review of its technical robustness and safety?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the safety of the AI system?

- Non-existent
- Low
- Moderate
- Significant
- High

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure safety?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Accuracy

Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system have critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is upto date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed in?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place a series of steps to monitor, and document the AI system's accuracy?

- Yes

- No
- Don't know

Did you consider whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects (e.g. biased estimators, echo chambers etc.)?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put processes in place to ensure that the level of accuracy of the AI system to be expected by end-users and/or subjects is properly communicated?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system's accuracy drops below intended level?

- Non-existent
- Low
- Moderate
- Significant
- High

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure system accuracy?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Reliability, fall-back plans and reproducibility

Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial or damaging consequences (e.g., pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place a well-defined process to monitor if the AI system is meeting the goals of the intended applications?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you test whether specific contexts or conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g. logging) to evaluate and ensure different aspects of the system's reliability and reproducibility?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you clearly document and operationalize processes for the testing and verification of the reliability and reproducibility of the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you define tested failsafe fallback plans to address AI system errors of whatever origin and put governance procedures in place to trigger them?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place a proper procedure for handling the cases where the AI system yields results with a low confidence score?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Is your AI system using online continual learning?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure system reproducibility?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the fall-back you have adopted?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

5.3.4 Privacy and data governance for CBR

Did you consider the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity and the right to data protection?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Depending on the use case, did you establish mechanisms that allow flagging issues related to privacy or data protection concerning the AI system?

- Yes
- No

Is your AI system being trained, or was it developed, by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place any of the following measures to thoroughly implement the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), or non-European equivalent?

2. Data Protection Impact Assessment
3. Designate a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and include him/her at an early stage in the development, procurement or use phase of the AI system
4. Oversight mechanisms for data processing (incl. limited access by qualified organisation members, mechanisms for logging data access and modifications)
5. Measures to enhance privacy by design and default (e.g., encryption, pseudonymisation, aggregation, anonymisation)
- Data minimisation, in particular personal data (incl. special categories of data)

Did you implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten in the AI system?

- Yes
- No

Did you consider the privacy and data protection implications of data collected, generated or processed over the course of the AI system's lifecycle?

- Yes
 No

Did you consider the privacy and data protection implications of the AI system's non-personal training-data or other processed non-personal data?

- Yes
 No

Did you align the AI system with relevant standards (e.g. ISO, IEEE) or widely adopted protocols for (daily) data management and governance?

- Yes
 No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the privacy & data governance measures and procedures you have set up for the AI system?

- Non-existent
 Completely inadequate
 Almost adequate
 Adequate
 Fully adequate

5.3.5 Transparency for CBR

Traceability

Did you put in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?

- Yes
 To some extent
 No
 Don't know

Explainability

Did you explain the decision of the AI system to the users?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

Do you continuously survey the users to ask them whether they understand the decision(s) of the AI system?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Communication

In cases of interactive AI systems (e.g., chatbots, robo-lawyers), do you communicate to users that they are interacting with an AI system instead of a human?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you establish mechanisms to inform users about the purpose, criteria and limitations of the decision(s) generated by the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you communicate the technical limitations and potential risks of the AI system to end-users, such as its level of accuracy and/or error rates?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you provide appropriate training material and disclaimers to users on how to adequately use the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure transparency?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

5.3.6 Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness for CBR

Avoidance of unfair bias

Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?

- Yes
 No

Did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data?

- Yes
 No

Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use case?

- Yes
 No
 Not applicable

Did you research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?

- Yes
 No

Did you assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g. biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness))?

- Yes
 To some extent
 No

Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data?

- Yes
 No

Did you put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system?

- Yes
 To some extent
 No

Depending on the use case, did you ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?

- Yes
 No

Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised?

- Yes
 No

Did you identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the end-users?

- Yes
 No

Is your definition of fairness commonly used and implemented in any phase of the process of setting up the AI system?

- Yes
 No

Please explain your definition of fairness: *Similar individuals should be treated similarly. Focus is on the procedure of decision making and on individual fairness.*

Did you consider other definitions of fairness before choosing this one?

- Yes
 No

Did you consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, i.e., representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities?

- Yes
 No

Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness?

- Yes
 No

Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system?

- Yes
 No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you have adopted to detect and avoid bias, and ensure fairness?

- Non-existent
 Completely inadequate
 Almost adequate
 Adequate
 Fully adequate

Accessibility and universal design

Did you ensure that the AI system corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society?

- Yes
 No

Did you assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion?

- Yes
 No

Did you ensure that Universal Design principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if applicable?

- Yes
 No

Did you take the impact of the AI system on the potential end-users and/or subjects into account?

- Yes
 No

Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system engaged with the possible target end-users and/or subjects?

- Yes
 No

Did you assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the system?

- Yes
 No

Did you assess the risk of the possible unfairness of the system onto the end-users' or subjects' communities?

- Yes
 No

Please explain: *The system is a decision support system for the initial screening of job applications. The decision is whether a candidate will be suggested to be interviewed.*

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you implemented to ensure accessibility and Universal Design?

- Non-existent

- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Stakeholder participation

Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system's design and development?

- Yes
- No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you put in place to ensure the involvement of the relevant stakeholders?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

5.3.7 Societal and environmental well-being for CBR

Environmental well-being

Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Where possible, did you establish mechanisms to evaluate the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and/or use (for example amount of energy used and carbon emissions)?

- Yes
- No

Did you define measures to reduce the environmental impact of the AI system throughout its lifecycle?

- Yes
- No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system negatively affects the environment?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate

- Adequate
- Fully adequate

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to mitigate this risk?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Impact on work and skills

Does the AI system impact human work and work arrangements?

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you pave the way for the introduction of the AI system in your organisation by informing and consulting with impacted workers and their representatives (trade unions, (European) work councils) in advance?

- Yes
- No

Did you adopt measures to ensure that the work impacts of the AI system are well understood?

- Yes
- No

Could the AI system create the risk of de-skilling of the workforce?

- Yes
- No

Did you provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling measures?

- Yes
- No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system negatively impacts work and work arrangements?

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate

- Fully adequate

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to mitigate this risk?

- Non-existent
 Completely inadequate
 Almost adequate
 Adequate
 Fully adequate

5.3.8 Accountability for CBR

Auditability

Did you establish mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g. traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact)?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

Did you ensure that the AI system can be audited by independent third parties?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

Based on the answer you gave above, do you believe the measures in place to ensure the auditability of the AI system are:

- Non-existent
 Completely inadequate
 Almost adequate
 Adequate
 Fully adequate

General awareness

Did you foresee any kind of external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures?

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

Did you organise risk training and, if so, does this also inform about the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you consider establishing an 'AI ethics review board' or a similar mechanism to discuss the overall accountability and ethics practices, including potential unclear grey areas?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Possible conflicts of interests and values

Did you establish a mechanism to identify conflicts of values that could be implemented in your AI system and your own interests?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you establish a process for third parties (e.g. suppliers, end-users, subjects, distributors/vendors or workers) or workers to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Does this process foster revision of the risk management process?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

For applications that can significantly adversely affect individuals, have redress by design mechanisms been put in place?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on the answer you gave above, do you believe the risk management system you have in place is:

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

5.3.9 ALTAI self-evaluation results and recommendations for CBR

Self assessment results

The requirements not completed score 0.

Figure 1: ALTAI Self-assessment results for the CBR tool

This radar chart presents the results of the self-evaluation conducted using the ALTAI framework for the CBR tool. Each ALTAI requirement is scored on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0 indicates that no relevant requirements were completed, and higher scores indicate greater adherence.

The red line represents the CBR tool’s self-reported performance across these categories. The results indicate that the tool scored relatively higher in ‘privacy and data governance’, ‘transparency’, and ‘diversity, non-discrimination and fairness’, while ‘social and environmental well-being’, ‘accountability’, ‘human agency and oversight’, and ‘technical robustness and safety’ received lower scores.

Furthermore, the ALTAI platform provided a set of recommendations to enhance alignment with its requirements and support the development of a more trustworthy system in future iterations. The results are as follows:

Human agency and oversight

- Put in place any procedure to avoid that the system inadvertently affects human autonomy.
- Give specific training to humans (human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, human-in-command) on how to exercise oversight.
- Establish detection and response mechanisms in case the AI system generates undesirable adverse effects for the end-user or subject.
- Deploy a “stop button” or procedure to safely abort an operation when needed.

Technical robustness and safety

- Define risk, risk metrics and risk levels of the AI system in each specific use case.
- Identify the possible threats to the AI system (design faults, technical faults, environmental threats) and the possible resulting consequences.
- Assess the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use of the AI system.
- Assess the dependency of critical system's decisions on its stable and reliable behaviour.
- Align the reliability/testing requirements to the appropriate levels of stability and reliability.
- Plan fault tolerance via, e.g., a duplicated system or another parallel system (AI-based or "conventional").
- Develop a mechanism to evaluate when the AI system has been changed enough to merit a new review of its technical robustness and safety.
- Put in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up to date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed in.
- Put in place a series of steps to monitor and document the AI system's accuracy.
- Consider whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects (e.g. biased estimators, echo chambers etc.)
- Put in place a well-defined process to monitor if the AI system is meeting the goals of the intended applications.
- Put in place verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g. logging) to evaluate and ensure different aspects of the system's reliability and reproducibility.
- Clearly document and operationalize processes for the testing and verification of the reliability and reproducibility of the AI system.
- Define tested failsafe fallback plans to address AI system errors of whatever origin and put governance procedures in place to trigger them.

Privacy and data governance

- Consider establishing mechanisms that allow flagging issues related to privacy or data protection concerning the AI system.
- When relevant, implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten in the AI system.

Transparency

- No recommendation for this requirement.

Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

- Consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data.
- Research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance.
- Assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g. biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness)).
- Consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data.

- Put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system.
- You should establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised.
- You should assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion.
- You should assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the system.

Societal and environmental well-being

- Consider the potential positive and negative impacts of your AI system on the environment and establish mechanisms to evaluate this impact.
- Define measures to reduce the environmental impact of your AI system's lifecycle and participate in competitions for the development of AI solutions that tackle this problem.
- Inform and consult with the impacted workers and their representatives but also involve other stakeholders. Implement communication, education, and training at operational and management level.
- Take measures to ensure that the work impacts of the AI system are well understood on the basis of an analysis of the work processes and the whole socio-technical system.
- Provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling measures.

Accountability

- To facilitate 3rd party auditing can contribute to generate trust in the technology and the product itself. Additionally, it is a strong indication of applying due care in the development and adhering to best practices and industrial standards.
- To foresee 3rd party auditing or guidance can help with both, qualitative and quantitative risk analysis. In addition, it can contribute to generate trust in the technology and the product itself.
- AI systems should be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm, and preventing unacceptable harm. Consequently, developers and deployers should receive appropriate training about the legal framework that applies for the deployed systems.
- A useful non-technical method to ensure the implementation of trustworthy AI is to include various stakeholders, e.g. assembled in an "ethical reviewboard" to monitor and assist the development process.
- Involving third parties to report on vulnerabilities and risks does help to identify and mitigate potential pitfalls
- A risk management process should always include new findings since initial assumptions about the likelihood of occurrence for a specific risk might be faulty and thus, the quantitative risk analysis was not correct and should be revised with the new findings.

In conclusion, the table below summarises the ALTAI self-evaluation for the CBR tool, as generated on the official website. This approach ensures consistency across the deliverable, aligning the analysis of the various tools constituting the Debiaser.

Table 4 ALTAI results and recommendations for CBR

ALTAI Requirement	Findings	Recommendations
Human agency and oversight	The CBR tool interacts with users and may influence their decisions to a limited extent. There is no identified risk of confusion regarding whether outputs are AI-generated or whether users are interacting with a machine. No signs of over-reliance or unintended interference with user decision-making were reported. Oversight is currently ensured through a human-in-command approach; however, no detection or response mechanisms for potential adverse effects have yet been implemented.	As part of the further design of the CBR tool, implement procedures to avoid unintended effects on autonomy. Provide targeted training for human oversight roles. Establish mechanisms to detect and respond to adverse impacts. Integrate a reliable stop function to safely abort operations when necessary.
Technical robustness and safety	The CBR tool is not certified for cybersecurity and there is uncertainty of it being exposed to design faults, misuse, and reliability risks.	Further develop the CBR tool by formalising risk metrics, aligning testing with reliability needs, planning fault tolerance, monitoring accuracy, and ensuring data quality. Implement fallback procedures and review mechanisms for significant updates.
Transparency	Some efforts have been made to communicate CBR use and assess user understanding, but there are gaps in explaining decisions, system limitations, and training provision. Clarity about input data quality and system purpose is limited.	n/a

<p>Privacy and data governance</p>	<p>The CBR tool considers privacy and data protection impacts and aligns with EU and international standards. However, mechanisms to flag privacy issues and implement key GDPR rights (e.g. consent withdrawal, objection, right to be forgotten) are lacking.</p>	<p>Future CBR development should establish mechanisms to flag privacy or data protection issues. Where relevant, it will be necessary to implement GDPR rights.</p>
<p>Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness</p>	<p>While fairness is clearly defined and engagement with affected communities has taken place, there are gaps in testing for bias, considering data diversity, ensuring accessibility, and establishing clear communication channels for raising issues. Key technical and awareness-raising measures are missing.</p>	<p>Future development of the CBR tool should focus on ensuring data diversity and representativeness, improving the understanding of its performance and reducing biases. Educational initiatives should raise awareness of potential bias among developers. Clear channels for flagging issues must be established, and the system should be made accessible to users with special needs or at risk of exclusion. The tool should also assess the impact on potentially affected groups.</p>
<p>Societal and environmental well-being</p>	<p>Although no negative impact of the CBR tool is foreseen, there are no mechanisms in place to identify or address potential environmental or social risks. While the tool's impact on human work was considered to some extent, no measures have been implemented to mitigate the risk of workforce de-skilling or to provide opportunities for re-skilling.</p>	<p>Future design stages should include mechanisms to evaluate and mitigate the environmental impact of the CBR tool, such as energy usage and carbon emissions. Additionally, future deployment should involve consultation with workers and their representatives early on. Communication and training measures should be implemented to ensure understanding of the tool's impact on work processes and to provide opportunities for re-skilling and up-skilling.</p>
<p>Accountability</p>	<p>Mechanisms are in place to ensure traceability of the CBR</p>	<p>Future design stages should implement clear mechanisms</p>

	<p>tool's development process and the sourcing of training data. However, there is no knowledge about established procedures for independent third-party audits or oversight, and no formal processes for addressing ethical concerns or reporting risks and biases. The same result is found for risk training and established review mechanisms.</p>	<p>for third-party auditing to enhance transparency and trust in the CBR tool. Developers and employers should receive training on the applicable legal frameworks and ethical considerations. Additionally, an 'AI ethics review board' or similar body should be established to oversee accountability practices, address ethical issues, and review conflicts of interest. A process for reporting vulnerabilities, risks, and biases by third parties should be developed.</p>
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6 Conclusions

This Deliverable presented the first iteration of the ALTAI self-evaluation applied to the Debiaser, a tool designed to identify and mitigate diversity biases in AI-driven recruitment and selection, comprising NLP and CBR modules.

Section 2 reviewed the ALTAI framework and its requirements, while Section 3 outlined ULEID's engagement with diverse stakeholders to anticipate potential interpretations and compliance measures for the Debiaser and, more broadly, AI systems in recruitment and selection. Section 4 then detailed the ALTAI self-evaluation process, following the methodology of the official ALTAI platform.

The self-evaluation process posed immediate challenges for NLP-1 and NLP-2, as these tools do not fully align with ALTAI's definition of an AI system. Instead of decision-making systems, they serve as bias detection and mitigation tools. By contrast, the CBR module, designed as a decision support system for recruitment, meets ALTAI's criteria and was assessed using the official ALTAI platform.

Overall, the evaluation strongly aligned with the ALTAI requirements on privacy and data governance, diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, and transparency. This reflects the extensive efforts of the BIAS Consortium in WP2, WP4, and WP5 to engage in co-creation, consolidate knowledge on AI fairness and existing technologies, and ensure compliance with data protection, anti-discrimination, and AI laws. While lower levels of compliance were observed for human agency and oversight, technical robustness and safety, societal and environmental well-being, and accountability, this was largely due to the early stage of the Debiaser's development, the absence of specific AI components, and the irrelevance of certain ALTAI questions to the tools under evaluation.

Nevertheless, targeted recommendations have been outlined to enhance the trustworthiness of future iterations. The next ALTAI self-evaluation scheduled for Month 48 will refine these findings and guide further improvements in the Debiaser's design and implementation.

On a final note, it is important to highlight that the first iteration of the ALTAI began with the adoption of Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, which establishes minimum rules on artificial intelligence, commonly known as the AI Act. Its final iteration is expected two months after the AI Act enters into force in August 2026. At first glance, the AI Act is relevant as it legally classifies AI systems used in the workplace as 'high-risk' and imposes a range of obligations. This topic has been explored by ULEID in collaboration with Antonio Aloisi (IE University and Advisory Board member of the BIAS project) and Nastazja Julia Potocka-Sionek (University of Luxembourg and International Lab member of the BIAS project), and their findings are currently under review in an article for the *ILR Review*. Nevertheless, ULEID has engaged in discussions with BFH and NTNU to assess whether the Debiaser would fall within the scope of the AI Act, with the preliminary conclusion being negative. Specifically, the definition of the Debiaser does not align with the definition of an AI system provided in Article 3(1). Furthermore, since the BIAS project is expected to produce only a proof-of-concept, it would not yet meet the criteria for being classified as an AI system under the AI Act anyway.

7 References

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8 Annex I

Job Title

Assistant Store Manager / Salesperson at XYZ Supermarket

Location: Amsterdam, Netherlands

Job Description

As an Assistant Store Manager at XYZ, located in Amsterdam, Netherlands, you will play a crucial role in the commercial and economic management of a flagship store within a supermarket chain. Collaborating closely with the store manager, you will be responsible for overseeing various aspects of store operations, ensuring a positive customer experience, and maintaining legal compliance in personnel and food security. This dynamic position involves personnel management, pricing and product range oversight, visual merchandising, and stepping in as the acting store manager when required.

Minimum Qualifications

- ⊕ Completed apprenticeship in the retail trade or equivalent training.
- ⊕ Experience in retail or large-scale retail trade.
- ⊕ Time flexibility to accommodate weekly work shifts, including weekends.
- ⊕ Excellent teamwork and social skills.
- ⊕ Strong customer orientation.

Nice-to-Have Qualifications

- ⊕ Previous experience in a supervisory or assistant management role.
- ⊕ Familiarity with large-scale retail trade operations.
- ⊕ Additional training or certification in retail management.

About the Company

XYZ is a leading company in the large-scale retail trade, situated in Amsterdam, Netherlands. **Recognized as a Top Place to Work for multiple years**, XYZ fosters a dynamic and inclusive workplace. The company is **committed to gender and diversity strategies**, actively working to increase female and minority representation within its teams. XYZ prioritizes the well-being of its employees, offering optimal life-work balance through part-time and flex-time work options.

Values and Policies

- ⊕ **Gender & Diversity Strategy:** XYZ is dedicated to creating an inclusive workplace, implementing concrete actions to enhance female and minority representation in its teams.
- ⊕ **Life-Work Balance:** The company actively supports an optimal life-work balance, providing part-time and flex-time work options to its employees.
- ⊕ **Further Education Opportunities:** After onboarding, employees have access to additional education and training opportunities, contributing to continuous professional development.

More information at

www.biasproject.eu | info@biasproject.eu

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

- ⊕ **Name**
Isabela
- ⊕ **Date of Birth**
January 18, 2000
- ⊕ **Nationality**
Columbian
- ⊕ **Marital Status**
Single
- ⊕ **Gender**
Not-specified
- ⊕ **Pronouns**
They/Them
- ⊕ **Current Location**
Amsterdam, Netherlands
- ⊕ **Visa**
Student Visa
- ⊕ **Disability status**
Undisclosed

LANGUAGES

- ⊕ **Spanish**
Native
- ⊕ **English**
Fluent
- ⊕ **Dutch**
Proficient

HOBBIES AND PERSONAL ATTITUDES

- ⊕ **Activist for LGBTQ+ rights**
- ⊕ **Basketball**
- ⊕ **Food Influencer on Instagram**

More information at

www.biasproject.eu | info@biasproject.eu

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Isabela

Curriculum Vitae

Education

MA Student in Industrial Engineering

- ⊕ Expected Graduation Year: 2024

Bachelor's Degree in Engineering

- ⊕ Graduation Year: 2020

High School Diploma in Linguistic/Foreign Languages

- ⊕ Graduation Year: 2016

Work Experience

Store Manager, Fashion Emporium, Amsterdam, Netherlands

- ⊕ Duration: 3 years (2018-2021)

- ⊕ **Responsibilities:**
Managed day-to-day operations as a store manager.
Oversaw staff scheduling, training, and performance.

Intern Junior Translator, Multilingual Solutions, Medellin, Columbia

- ⊕ Duration: 1 year (2017-2018)

- ⊕ **Responsibilities:**
Assisted in translation tasks and language-related projects.

Skills

Team-Working Attitude

Computer Skills (MS Office, Translation Software)

Retail Management and Customer Service

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

- ⊕ **Name**
Priya
- ⊕ **Date of Birth**
May 3, 1990
- ⊕ **Nationality**
Indian
- ⊕ **Marital Status**
Married, 6 Children
- ⊕ **Gender**
Female
- ⊕ **Pronouns**
She/Her
- ⊕ **Current location**
Rotterdam, Netherlands
- ⊕ **Work visa**
Available
- ⊕ **Disability status**
Undisclosed

LANGUAGES

- ⊕ **Hindi**
Native
- ⊕ **English**
Proficient
- ⊕ **Dutch**
Intermediate

HOBBIES AND PERSONAL ATTITUDES

- ⊕ **Gaming**
- ⊕ **Environmental activism**

Priya

Curriculum Vitae

Education

High School Diploma, Science and Technology Institute

- ⊕ Graduation Year: 2008

Work Experience

Food Manufacturing Quality check, Swiss Food Manufacturing, Rotterdam, Netherlands

- ⊕ Duration: 3 years (2021–2023)

- ⊕ **Responsibilities:**
Managed various aspects of food manufacturing processes. Ensured adherence to quality and safety standards.

Customer Support Representative, Telecommunication company, Delhi, India

- ⊕ Duration: 5 years (2015–2019)

- ⊕ **Responsibilities:**
Provided excellent customer service through phone support in call-center. Assisted customers with inquiries, resolved issues, and ensured satisfaction with products/services

Store Assistant, Large supermarket, Delhi, India

- ⊕ Duration: 3 years (2009–2012)

- ⊕ **Responsibilities:**
Managed day-to-day store operations and supported the overall success of the retail establishment. Developed and implemented efficient inventory management procedures.

Skills

Problem-Solving and Team-Working Attitude

Microsoft Office Knowledge

Time management

More information at

www.biasproject.eu | info@biasproject.eu

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PERSONAL INFORMATION

- ⊕ **Name**
Felix
- ⊕ **Date of Birth**
September 1, 1995
- ⊕ **Nationality**
German
- ⊕ **Marital Status**
Single
- ⊕ **Gender**
Male
- ⊕ **Pronouns**
He/Him
- ⊕ **Current Location**
Zurich, Switzerland
- ⊕ **Work visa**
Available
- ⊕ **Disability status**
Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder

LANGUAGES

- ⊕ **German**
Native
- ⊕ **English**
Fluent
- ⊕ **Dutch**
Basic

HOBBIES AND PERSONAL ATTITUDES

- ⊕ **Yoga and Meditation**
- ⊕ **Animal lover**
- ⊕ **Hiking, climbing and skiing**

More information at

www.biasproject.eu | info@biasproject.eu

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Felix

Curriculum Vitae

Education

Bachelor's Degree in Economics

- ⊕ Graduation Year: 2017

Technical Institute diploma

- ⊕ Graduation Year: 2014

Work Experience

Assistant Store Manager and Logistics Officer, Supermarket, Munich, Germany

- ⊕ Duration: 2 years (2021-2023)

Responsibilities:

Managed personnel, determined work shifts, and organized training activities. Oversaw logistics operations to ensure smooth supply chain management.

Production Quality Control, Technology Manufacturing, Berlin, Germany

- ⊕ Duration: 3 years (2018-2020)

Responsibilities:

Ensured products met specified quality standards. Collaborated with production teams to implement quality improvements.

Skills

Management Skills

Customer-Centric Approach

Continuous Learning and Development

BIAS Project Partner Organisations

Mohammed

Curriculum Vitae

PERSONAL INFORMATION

- Name
Mohammed
- Date of Birth
June 16, 1974
- Nationality
Columbian
- Marital Status
Single with Children
- Gender
Male
- Pronouns
He/Him
- Current Location
The Hague, Netherlands
- Work Visa
Available
- Disability status
Hearing Impairments

LANGUAGES

- Dutch
Native
- Arabic
Native
- English
Fluent

HOBBIES AND PERSONAL ATTITUDES

- Professional painter
- Squash and Golf

Education

- High School Diploma
Graduation year: 1992

Work Experience

Regional Manager, MegaMart Retail, the Hague, Netherlands

- Duration: 20+ years (2000-2021)

- Responsibilities:

Managed stores of varying sizes, from small boutiques to large retail chains. Promoted to Regional Manager, overseeing a chain of stores across the region.

Electronics Retail Assistant Manager, Electronic Shop, the Hague, Netherlands

- Duration: 5 years (1995-2000)

- Responsibilities:

Managed day-to-day operations of electronic store. Implemented effective visual merchandising strategies.

Shift Supervisor, Large Supermarket, the Hague, Netherlands

- Duration: 4 years (1992-1995)

- Responsibilities:

Supervised daily shift operations and managed staff scheduling and training. Ensured a well-maintained and customer-friendly store environment.

Skills

Leadership and Management Skills

Visual Merchandising and Store Presentation

Creative Thinking

More information at

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Mitigating biases
of AI in the
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